

WoodCircus

Underpinning the vital role of the forest-based
sector in the Circular Bioeconomy

D3.2

Innovative Practices of Wood Industries in the Circular Economy in Europe

WP3 final report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Engineered wood products are becoming more recognized in the Circular Economy as climate friendly, sustainable alternative for use in construction (new build or renovation), furniture, interiors, and a range of innovative applications. Wood products can effectively store potentially large amounts of carbon and keep them in reuse and recycling loops for a long time through additional lifecycle phases. Wood products are thus expected to play a major role in the decarbonization of the building sector and other industries. However, huge amounts of resources are currently still wasted or used inefficiently, which is why the wood sector needs to learn from good practices and adopt innovative circular solutions across the value chain.

This report provides an overview of the large variety in the wood sector regarding different circular operational concepts and technological progress, including efficiency and processing, reuse and recycling, to waste and side stream valorisation. The identified solutions are categorized based on the 9R-Principles of the European Commission's *Categorisation System for the Circular Economy (CSCE)*. In a Europe-wide open call, companies in the wood sector were identified, to present their solutions and business concepts for efficiency, recovery and circularity as relevant practices. The results are described in 29 company factsheets, summarizing the innovative features of each business practice in a visual, easily readable layout. The collection represents a good snapshot of showcases of the ongoing transformation in the forest-based sector towards more circular models.

In conclusion, the adoption of Circular Economy concepts in the forest-based sector is showing progress, although it is yet far from mainstream. The company cases demonstrate how material loops can be closed and how residues and products in the use cycle can either be directly reused or fed back into the production cycle, mitigating direct incineration or landfill. For closing the loops, larger leading market actors and network organisations will play a decisive role, because they can attain the capacity to connect with a critical mass of other market actors and can leverage benefits along a managed supply chain to optimize resources and value added. Most of the described solutions are transferable and can thus inspire local companies or joint initiatives to foster the broader uptake of the Circular Economy across Europe.

WoodCircus is a Horizon 2020 funded project aimed to increase knowledge, raise awareness and improve conditions for a wider uptake of resource efficient processing and recycling solutions in wood-based value chains, fostering higher competitiveness of the European forest-based sector. The project was carried out from 2018 to 2021 by 17 partners including seven research organizations, five industrial partners and three representative European organizations.

WoodCircus repository: zenodo.org/communities/woodcircus

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1 Purpose and objectives

The WoodCircus project was funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820892. The overall goal is to increase knowledge, raise awareness and improve conditions for an uptake of resource efficient processing and recycling in wood-based value chains, and strengthen competitiveness of the European woodworking sector within the Circular Economy.

The construction sector has an enormous economic and social significance for the EU, providing 18 million direct jobs and contributing about 9% of the EU's GDP. A major share of the wood in the EU is used in construction and furnishings; thus the construction sector represents one of the biggest sources of waste in terms of volume with approximately 70.5 million tons of wood waste generated annually. Currently, only a fraction of waste wood is recycled. The rest is landfilled or incinerated, noting that there exist large differences between EU member states in efficiency and technology readiness as well as in legal, policy and socioeconomic framework.

To improve process efficiency and to enhance conscious management of natural resources, there is a need to assess the wood sector's circularity and to identify transferable good practices to increase the recovery and reuse of raw materials. Resource efficiency and cascade use of virgin wood, waste wood and side streams are key levers to improve environmental, economic and social sustainability. Therefore, the WoodCircus project identified, assessed and disseminated a range of good practices and innovations in the woodworking sector. Addressing their performance and validating relevant transferable solutions, the results offer evidence and tangible information for market actors, stakeholders and policymakers.

A variety of innovative, efficient solutions exist in companies, but are mostly known only at national or local level. WoodCircus conducted a Europe-wide 'Open Call for Innovative Practices' (WP3) targeting companies in wood processing, reuse and recycling. The aim was to identify and collect a broad range of representative tried and tested solutions and business concepts in SMEs and larger companies that are suitable for broader dissemination. Launched with the support from various associated EU and national stakeholder organisations, the open call identified in total 29 company cases at different stages in the wood value chain and from different EU regions. These cases were assessed using the 9R Principles of the EC CSCE framework to describe their role in a coherent way, and factsheets for public dissemination were developed.

The work was led by InnovaWood together with coordinator VTT and FCBA. Regional consortium partners and the Advisory Board supported the dissemination across European regions. The identified innovative practices were also considered in WP2, WP4 and WP5, of which some cases were studied further using LCA.

2 9R Principles: Categorisation framework for the Circular Economy

2.1 CSCE framework

For the business sector, the transformation to the Circular Economy means both disruptive challenges in production and customer relations, but also huge market opportunities. To increase understanding and adoption of this large paradigm shift, the European Commission has recently provided a conceptual framework to business approaches: the 9R principles (short: 9Rs) in a *Categorisation System for the Circular Economy (CSCE)*¹. The 9Rs basically represent an extension of the well-known 3Rs principles commonly referred to as 'reduce, reuse, recycle', providing a more detailed classification for different types of sustainable use of resources.

To better characterize and structure the innovative practices as meaningful cases for the forest-based sector, the 9R principles were applied to the collection of 29 company cases. The 9R framework, developed by the CE Finance Expert Group for the European Commission, represents a clear, applicable method to qualify and rank quite different technological approaches in terms of the level of circularity (Figure 1).

<i>Impact on circularity</i>	<i>Focus of material use</i>
R1 Refuse	Choose alternative product
R2 Rethink	Intensify use of product
R3 Reduce	Use less material per product
R4 Reuse	Use same product 'as is'
R5 Repair	Replace defective parts
R6 Refurbish	Reuse parts in upcycling
R7 Remanufacture	Reuse parts in same product
R8 Repurpose	Recover parts for different product
R9 Recycle	Recover materials
Energy recovery *	Convert to energy

Figure 1 Hierarchy of 9R principles (own figure based on CSCE, EC 2021)

* mentioned, but not considered as true circular principle

¹ European Commission, 2021. Categorisation system for the circular economy. A sector-agnostic categorisation system for activities substantially contributing to the circular economy. Independent expert report, edited by Peter Hirsch and Christian Schempp. EC DG Research and Innovation. 20 pages. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ca9846a8-6289-11ea-b735-01aa75ed71a1>

All nine principles contribute directly or indirectly to increasing resource efficiency and decreasing environmental impacts. Similar to the 3Rs, the 9Rs also reflect a decreasing ranking order of priority from R1 (high) to R9 (low) (Table 1). The same logic applies: forms of use of a higher order are considered more impactful to reduce resource consumption, because resources saved do not enter the processing chain and consequently do not have to be dealt with in steps of the subsequent lower orders. The 9R principles are especially useful for characterisation and orientation of production systems. They can be applied more easily by companies as for example detailed product Life Cycle Assessments (LCA), which require a lot of data and context specific analyses.

Table 1 Definition of the 9R Circular Economy principles of the CSCE (EC 2021)

No.	Principle	Short definition
R1	Refuse	Make product redundant by abandoning its function or by offering the same function by a radically different (e.g., digital) product or service.
R2	Rethink	Make product use more intensive (e.g., through product-as-a service, reuse and sharing models or by putting multi-functional products on the market).
R3	Reduce	Increase efficiency in product manufacture or use by consuming fewer natural resources and materials.
R4	Reuse	Reuse of a product which is still in good condition and fulfils its original function (and is not waste) for the same purpose for which it was conceived.
R5	Repair	Repair and maintenance of defective product so it can be used with its original function.
R6	Refurbish	Restore an old product and bring it up to date (to specified quality level).
R7	Remanufacture	Use parts of a discarded product in a new product with the same function (and as-new-condition).
R8	Repurpose	Use a redundant product or its parts in a new product with different function.
R9	Recycle	Recover materials from waste to be reprocessed into new products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does <i>not</i> include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations.

Figure 2 Circular Economy processes based on value retention loops (UNEP 2021)²

Explanation: 1) User-to-user processes: shorter loop, where a product or component remains close to its user and function; 2) User-to-business processes: medium/long loop, where a product or component is upgraded and producers involved again; 3) Business-to-business processes: long loop, where a product or component loses its original function.

Some important aspects of these principles must be highlighted (cf. Figure 2):

- *R1-Refuse* is the first priority and substantial extension of the 3Rs. It advocates to first question the use of a product or service. If it is unsustainable, the use should be abandoned and a better/cleaner alternative should be adopted (e.g., use a bicycle instead of a car). In the context of the forest-based sector, *R1-Refuse* first and foremost relates to the substitution of other materials that require a lot of energy for their production (e.g., concrete, steel). This is a decisive advantage of wood, and a main argument to promote engineered wood products as climate-friendly, nature-based solution.
- *R2-Rethink*, the second principle, comprises all alternative business models and ways of using products and materials more intensively, including a focus on closing the loop directly between user and producer. For example, buy back schemes for furniture from customers can allow to reintegrate a used product as

² UNEP circularity platform 2021. [buildingcircularity.org](https://www.buildingcircularity.org)

a resource in the production of new furniture. Both R1 and R2 should be considered thoroughly before choosing any of the lower categories, because foregoing negative impacts (e.g., emissions) by replacing fully or partially the material or use is the best strategy for reducing resource consumption.

- *R3-Reduce* is the third best option and refers to using less resources and/or with higher efficiency. A typical example in the wood industry is to increase the yield of wood processing by using higher performing technology (e.g., thinner saw blades, higher throughput). However, as such 'classic' performance improvements allow companies to increase competitiveness and market share, this principle bears the 'risk' of economic growth eventually leading to higher resource consumption.
- The principles R4 Reuse to R9-Recycle refer to the same 3Rs-idea of closing the value cycle, and preventing incineration or landfill, with a gradual priority shift from reusing as much as possible a *product* towards reusing the *materials* that a product is made of. In circular thinking, product reuse clearly has a higher priority over material reuse, because more original value is preserved, and less transformation and less energy input are required. Indeed, this prioritisation is key to make the Circular Economy work because it helps identifying *in the first place* those opportunities with the highest potential for increasing resource efficiency and decreasing environmental impacts.

Finally, it must be noted that energy recovery has not been included as a tenth principle of Circular Economy in the 9Rs. The CSCE report acknowledges "*the recovery of (embodied) energy from wastes and residues including resource efficiency gains from waste-to-energy and waste-to-fuel strategies as fairly modest in comparison with the other 9Rs particularly when considering the loss in economic value of potentially recyclable materials through incineration*" (EC 2021, p.7).

This reflects the continuous debate on the subject. The position here is that not accounting for energy recovery as a suitable option leads to identifying beneficial solutions along the 9Rs, which would most probably not have been considered in a more business-as-usual thinking approach.

2.2 Main features of 9R principles in the wood sector

This chapter addresses each of the 9Rs with a condensed interpretation of the main topics of relevance in the wood sector and the relevant identified practice examples. The 29 company cases were grouped per type of product (or subsector) within the wood industry, and each of the 9R principles was checked if and to which extent it has been applied in the specific business case (cf. Table 2).

Table 2 Mapping of identified innovative practices per the 9Rs of the CSCE

Type of product	Company	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9
Wood-based panels	Rilegno IT			■					■	■
	Unilin BE			■						■
	MDF Recovery UK			■						■
	Egger RO			■						■
	Gutex DE			■				■		■
	FagusGrecon DE			■						
Furniture, interiors, solid wood products	GFC SE		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	Valdelia FR		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	Holy wood BE			■			■	■	■	■
	Herso NL			■				■	■	■
	Melu SI			■					■	■
	M Sora SI			■					■	■
	Webo NL			■		■			■	■
	Donar SI			■		■				■
	Zunami UA			■						■
Wood construction	Sofrinnov FR	■	■	■	■			■	■	■
	Tschopp CH	■		■				■	■	
	Aalto Haitek FI	■		■				■	■	
	CREE AT	■		■					■	
	Lignotrend DE	■		■					■	
	Fagus Suisse CH	■		■					■	
	Termowood NO	■		■					■	
Special products, sidestream uses	R. Beck DE	■		■					■	■
	Holzmühle DE	■		■						■
	Orineo BE	■		■						■
	Accys NL	■		■				■		
	Fearmaga ES			■					■	
Smart tools	RFIDirect UK			■						■
	GFA ES			■						■

Note: The innovative practices were categorized based on the available information in the application forms and additional materials provided by the companies. It represents an interpretation by the authors to their best understanding of each business case, yet certain features may have been omitted in the material. See Annex Table 9 for further details on the assessment of each company case.

2.2.1 R1-Refuse

Make product redundant by abandoning its function or by offering the same function by a radically different (e.g., digital) product or service.

Throughout the past century, everyday products that were traditionally made of wood, have been replaced gradually by all sorts of synthetic and composite materials, because these offered technical advantages or better cost-benefit ratios. Today however, wood solutions, including composites and engineered wood products, experience a renaissance as a renewable biomaterial: wood is appreciated for its, strength, insulation properties and aesthetics, plus its benefits for climate protection.

Consequently, the Refuse principle applies to all those wood-based products which do replace (or you could consider it as 'reoccupy') products or use functions which are dominated by fossil-based or other carbon-intensive materials nowadays. The level of impact that this replacement can have depends however also on the specific carbon footprint of the products to be replaced. In most applications where we find a lot of wood still today, such as roof trusses or furniture, fossil-based materials did never play a similar, dominant role. Consequently, such products or functions can only have a limited replacement effect and should not be represented under the Refuse principle (e.g., furniture products are a 'mixed bag': some use a lot of wood, some none at all).

In addition, it should be noted that wood-based products do not per se perform better than other materials in detailed product comparisons (e.g., LCA): carbon footprints are highly context-dependent, and energy-extensive production systems or products can also be found in the wood sector.

Considering this historic context, the Refuse principle applies mainly to the construction sector, where modern engineered wood solutions do outperform the established concrete-based systems when parameters of circularity such as carbon footprints are compared. All 7 identified innovative practices of wood construction companies can be assigned to principle R1. Yet it should be noted that 6 out of 7 practices use virgin wood (i.e., timber harvested in forest), so these are not about using recycled raw materials. The reason is that virgin wood is the most reliable option for load bearing structures, especially for glued elements (e.g., Cross Laminated Timber CLT). But because such massive products store high amounts of carbon, their beneficial climate impact is evident.

Nevertheless, most building codes (e.g., Eurocode 5) do not refer to and do not require virgin wood. In theory, this leaves room for considering recovered wood also for load bearing structures in the future. It remains the challenge for applied R&D to assess the mechanical strengths of glued elements after several decades of use to provide evidence and proof under which conditions these can be reused again for wood construction.

Reusing recovered wood in construction would enhance climate benefits even more. This would have a coupled effect of R1 and all principles from R4-Reuse to R8-Repurpose. A first example is the innovative practice of *Sofrinnov* (company case no. 3.1), which uses recovered wood to establish one-storey buildings, because here loads are limited and not a critical factor.

The principle R1-Refuse also applies to more specific wood products. Three of such innovative practices were identified:

- Lignoloc wooden nails by *Raimund Beck KG* (no. 4.1) are a substitute for steel nails in wooden construction elements. These nails, which are officially approved for load bearing structures, are produced from virgin beech wood that is densified to increase the mechanical properties. They function as reliable connectors for wood construction elements based on a chemo-mechanical welding process. After fulfilling their function, these nails will remain as inclusions inside the wooden construction elements, and they will not limit further processing of the elements by standard wood working machines. Therefore, these nails constitute a substantial improvement in circular design compared to steel nails, considering also all principles from R4-Reuse, to R9-Recycle.
- Other plant-based materials, both grinded and/or chemically modified forms, can substitute their fossil-based equivalents, while storing carbon and lowering environmental impacts. The company *Orineo* (no. 4.3) produces natural binders as plant-based adhesive and matrix for bio-composites as plastic alternatives. *Holzmühle Westerkamp* (no. 4.2) provides wood flour and fibres that are a starting material for a wide range upcycled high tech applications as filter aids or for animal feeding. However, although reprocessing of the final materials (e.g., composites) is possible at the end of the life cycle, it remains open to what extent closing this material loop occurs in practice.
- Other companies such as wooden window or furniture producers may also substitute less sustainable materials. However, because an impact assessment under principle R1-Refuse is rather complex and context-dependent, these innovative practices are allocated mainly to R3-Reduce and R8-Repurpose.

2.2.2 R2-Rethink

Make product use more intensive (e.g., through product-as-a service, reuse and sharing models or by putting multi-functional products on the market).

Rethink means maximising the added value of a product not strictly in economic terms (e.g., RoI), but in terms of resource-benefit ratio for users. The focus of Rethink approaches lies on changes in the business models including those closing the loop directly between user and producer (Figure 2); technological developments are merely enablers (e.g., industry 4.0 tools, apps).

The challenges for harnessing the potential of these approaches are substantial, because both producers and users must go through a profound shift of mind-set:

- Producers maintain the ownership of materials or products. This means they are now responsible of rethinking the entire life cycle of their product including all steps after use: disassembly, reuse and recycling possibilities for closing the material loop.
- Users lose ownership of materials and products and will change the ways they identify with them. Moreover, they might be monitored/evaluated about their use behaviour and maintenance of the products. Rating systems define the producer's buy-back value at the end of a use phase when, instead of simply throwing it away, users must return the product back to the producer or hand it over to another user.

Entering the market with such novel business approaches is a challenge, as most market actors still focus on linear business models. Another challenge is that for products with rather long-term use cycles (e.g., 15 years for wooden furniture, or 25+ years for building products), producers have to deal with long market feedback loops. Because the market response is so slow, producers cannot use rapid tests for Rethink prototypes, but have to develop a solid long-term vision and a consistent network of business partners.

Among the collected practices, three can be identified as Rethink approaches:

- The company *Green Furniture Concept* (no. 2.1) provides circular furniture for interior in public areas, and relies on different leasing, maintenance and buy-back concepts. GFC has successfully implemented R2 in its business model on the European and partly world-wide market.
- *Sofrinno* (no. 3.1) is a shelter and leisure house producer and works with used pallets as main building component for their constructions. They combine recovered materials in a modular way which guarantees easy assembly and disassembly. After first use as building elements, all components are still intact and can be reused again for construction or their original purpose packaging.
- *Valdelia* (no. 2.2) is a French network organisation that gives value to used professional furniture by closing the loop in four ways: second-hand retail, re-use, upcycling, and material recycling. Recuperating used professional furniture as main resource, Valdelia intervenes where most furniture producers do not see a market: sorting and re-distributing used furniture to the most appropriate reuse or recycling streams. The key is that such market actors are active on both ends: they redirect material flows back into the use and production cycles, and they accompany producers to adopt more circular design and marketing models.

2.2.3 R3-Reduce

Increase efficiency in product manufacture or use by consuming fewer natural resources and materials.

The Reduce principle tackles efficiency increases of material and energy consumption on all levels of the company, including supply (material type, quality, logistics), processing level (more efficient machines and processes), distribution (types of transport, logistics), and also organisation of work including staff trainings. Measures to improve efficiency have always been and are still the most common approach of companies to increase their competitiveness and market share. Numerous business management and optimization systems rely largely on such efficiency approaches. Their main focus is, however, to reduce the resource consumption per unit. But this does not necessarily aim at or lead to an overall reduction in resource consumption in a market, especially when the business is upscaling and the market is growing. Still, Reduce approaches contribute to the circular economy in a meaningful way, especially when they are applied in combination with other principles of the 9Rs: then they can leverage important gains or advantages to reach the competitiveness of alternative circular business approaches.

It is therefore no surprise that all identified 29 innovative practices relate in one way or the other to the Reduce principle: all include some aspect of technological innovation that leads to an improvement of the process or the product, both in technological performance or better exploitation of the raw material, and which results in the end to savings of input material per output unit. Higher performance and material savings are the main goal of some practices, e.g., the machinery manufacturer *FagusGrecon* (no. 1.6). Others apply the Reduce principle as a side benefit while their main focus is on another principle.

2.2.4 R4-Reuse

Reuse of a product which is still in good condition and fulfils its original function (and is not waste) for the same purpose for which it was conceived.

Reusing a product for resource savings has obvious benefits: prolonging the use time of a product means extending its life cycle and reducing the need for materials to replace the 'old' with a new but similar product. However, because technological progress advances so rapidly and is key to a company's competitiveness, buying the latest version of a product or equipment (e.g., digital manufacturing) is in many cases a critical decision for the company to ensure or enhance its market position. Reusing becomes the second-best option, especially when consumers demand high quality or competitive prices.

Secondly, also environmental impacts of reusing a product might be a concern, if the new version has a better environmental performance per unit.

This dilemma remains difficult to assess and requires detailed LCA approaches including projections into the future for thorough decision making today.

Still, if whole industry sectors continue to chase only 'the brand new', we will never solve the massive waste problems that have far reaching impacts of the earth's ecosystems and people's health and livelihoods. This is a global problem, and it is to a large extent also the industry's responsibility to develop and offer products that facilitate reuse, to integrate this principle fully into their business philosophy and to communicate it to their customers.

To take a first step and solve this question partly on a product level, companies can look for solutions to 'redirect' used products which are still fully functional for the same purpose to new clients of specific markets (second-hand, second user). Unless the products must be transported over long distances or require complicated logistics, these approaches are generally more efficient than R5 to R9, because the products can be used again 'as is' without much intervention necessary.

The identified innovative practices of *Valdelia*, *Green Furniture Concept* and *Sofrinnov* are examples that have well implemented the Reuse principle.

2.2.5 R5-Repair

Repair and maintenance of defective product so it can be used with its original function.

Repair and maintenance of products is currently experiencing a renaissance in many markets, thanks to digitalisation and smart products that inform the user and/or the producer at the right moment when to repair or change a piece. Platforms which facilitate to do business with repair as a service are also growing rapidly. Repair should occur when it is also most resource efficient from the life cycle point of view. In the end, such approaches must not be too complicated for the customer and show a clear cost effectiveness, which are currently the main barriers for wider application.

Among the identified practices, the companies *Green Furniture Concept* (no. 2.1), *Valdelia* (no. 2.2), *Webo* (no. 2.7) and *Donar* (no. 2.8) are examples where repair approaches for their furniture and wooden windows are incorporated into their business concept. The focus of these practices is the circular product design of modular systems in the first place, which are also enabled for easy replacement of dysfunctional parts during the lifetime.

This modular approach accounts to some extent for the dilemma caused by technological progress described under R4-Reuse. Modular products that can be easily repaired allow to keep pace with technological advances if up to date versions of the replaceable parts can be selected for repair. This is much more resource efficient than exchanging the entire product.

2.2.6 R6-Refurbish

Restore an old product and bring it up to date (to specified quality level).

Refurbishment is about upcycling recovered material in a product of good quality and/or with higher functionality than the original product. It is an important new trend concerning all kinds of materials, including typical wood products, which find new applications after upcycling. Refurbishment solutions often go together with R7-Remanufacture and R8-Repurpose principles. In a broader sense, the Refurbish principle also includes wood as a material that is practical to refurbish other products. Especially in the building sector wood is often used for modular separation walls, building annexes or thermal insulation purposes.

The R6-Refurbish principle applies to the following identified good practices:

- *Holy Wood* (no. 2.3), *Herso* (no. 2.4) and *Green Furniture Concept* (no. 2.1) produce upcycled furniture.
- *Valdelia* (no. 2.2) supplies products and material to upcycled furniture manufacturers.
- *Gutex* wood fibre insulation panels (no. 1.5) and *Accoya* ultra-durable modified wood (no. 4.4) are suitable for exterior wall insulation. Such products are integrated for example in rear-ventilated façade systems designed to refurbish a building so that it reaches the latest energy efficiency standards.

2.2.7 R7-Remanufacture

Use parts of a discarded product in a new product with the same function (and as-new-condition).

Remanufacture focuses on creating products that include used parts recovered from other products. Like R6-Refurbish, it also refers to upcycling, and these approaches are important attempts today to close the loop of material flows. However, all of them are limited by the fact that today, product parts are in general not yet based on circular design (e.g., design for disassembly) and are therefore challenging for easy remanufacturing activities. Especially in the case of furniture, which are quite complex products, substantial logistical effort is required to recover reusable parts.

In the construction sector, more and more high-end solutions for sustainable building including eliminating potentially harmful substances are emerging. But because buildings have a long lifetime (several decades), companies hardly consider circularity in a holistic manner: they mostly neglect to consider disassembly and reintroduction of material into the production cycle, although there could be plenty of remanufacture and repurpose possibilities. Buildings are not yet designed for proper

dismantling or deconstruction without creating huge amounts of waste. For example, timber in old buildings that is still structurally intact could potentially be remanufactured, but because the recovery is too difficult and costly, it is usually destroyed during the demolition phase of the building.

For companies it is difficult to integrate the Remanufacture principle today in a short to medium term economic perspective, because positive environmental impacts mostly materialise in the use and after-use phases, and the market response allowing to access those materials again for remanufacture is very long-term. Wood construction companies also give low priority to such long-term strategic goals, because within the global wood construction boom, they are growing fast and currently have only limited capacities to engage with a deeper transformation towards circular business models.

The Remanufacture principle applies to the following companies:

- *Holy Wood, Herso, Green Furniture Concept* and *Valdelia* are examples of furniture remanufacturing.
- *Green Furniture Concept* is the most advanced example, because their business concept allows to bypass the constraint of lacking circular design of furniture: through their buy-back and maintenance scheme, they ensure to recover their own material from their clients. Nevertheless, if more reusable parts and material could be obtained also from other companies, they could increase the share of recovered material in their products even more.
- *Tschopp Holzbau* (no. 3.2), *Aalto Haitek* (no. 3.3) and *Sofrinnov* (no. 3.1) are examples of building products based modular concepts that allow the reuse of the elements in the same application (because they do not require adhesives as binding elements). They are thus also suitable to shorten the use-cycles if needed, as disassembly requires comparatively little effort.

2.2.8 R8-Repurpose

Use a redundant product or its parts in a new product with different function.

The Repurpose principle is about finding any remaining reuse option for a product or its parts, before it goes to the last recovery stage of material recycling R9. This allows for a lot of creative applications and solutions to upcycle any remaining piece of a product, which may completely differ from the original purpose.

Regarding wood products, one of the main challenges is that the established supply, trade and waste streams are still too linear and that companies must undertake high efforts to acquire sufficient amounts of suitable reusable wood (reported for example by *M-Sora* and *Webo*).

However, if clean, toxic-free, well-sorted wood material could be recovered on a large scale from the construction sector to be directed back into the production cycle, this would represent a huge potential volume. For example, structural timber elements of larger dimensions that fulfil load-bearing purpose in buildings could become a valuable raw material for manufacturers of furniture, building products and other specialised solid wood products of high value.

While research is starting to explore such routes (e.g., possibilities of repurposing CLT cut-outs), the legal framework in most countries regarding waste regulations (e.g., exclusion of used wood that might contain pollutions) are an additional barrier to foster such needed innovations to upscale the Circular Economy.

- About half of the 29 identified practices apply the Repurpose principle in one or another way.
- An exceptional repurpose practice is *Fearmaga* in Spain (no. 4.5). They use mussel drafts built of large untreated eucalyptus beams which float for about 25 years on the sea. When this wood is reclaimed, it is highly appreciated by carpenters and cabinet makers for the unique, 'wild' appearance of the timber surface. It is repurposed into all sorts of wooden products, and it is an eye-opening demonstration of a unique supply chain that life cycles of wood material could effectively be extended for many years with quite low-tech solutions.

2.2.9 R9-Recycle

Recover materials from waste to be reprocessed into new products, materials or substances either for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations.

Recycling and valorisation of waste wood material is a core activity of many major companies in the wood sector, notably panel producers and special fibre producers. Their large factories require on a constant supply of substantial wood volumes. To assure the raw material supply, they rely not only on regular purchase, but they are also proactive in upstream waste management, e.g., via established networks and partnerships with public and private waste collectors.

These companies and their business ecosystem contribute decisively to recover significant fractions of waste wood streams for new production cycles. It should be noted that particleboards are the only product today allowing for large-scale wood recycling in industrial plants, hence their contribution to the current state of circularity in the sector is significant.

About two thirds of the identified innovative practices include recycling activities:

- *Unilin* (no. 2.1.2), *Egger* (no. 1.4) and members of *Rilegno* network (no. 1.1) are particle board manufacturers, managing large networks of waste wood suppliers.
- *Holzmühle Westerkamp* (no. 4.2) and *Orineo* (no. 4.3) convert and upcycle wooden side streams and other bio-based residues into source material for a wide range of applications.
- Among the other companies, many use recycled materials, reuse their own production rejects in their products and hand over their waste material to local recycling providers.

However, a large share of this recovered wood material would be potentially suitable for recycling in higher value-added products such as thermal insulation materials, which could generate much higher benefits for climate change mitigation through substitution, e.g., in the renovation of Europe's building stock. In terms of volumes involved, the impact could be enormous. First examples can be found where companies have initiated collection systems for cut-offs of insulation materials.

A main reason why such recycling practices are still limited is that wood waste streams are heterogeneous, often mixed with various other materials (e.g., demolition waste), and are therefore difficult to process. Innovating continuous industrial recycling processes for wood requires large investments in R&D, new facilities, not to mention the risk of limited market uptake. However, these technical barriers are already being tackled, e.g., by manufacturers of smart sorting equipment. Another major factor is that the recovery of the embodied energy of waste wood is an economically attractive option, because it is considered as renewable alternative to fossil fuel (see following chapter).

2.2.10 Recovery of embodied energy

As mentioned in chapter 3.1, the CSCE Expert Group does not consider the recovery of embodied energy from wastes and residues as a true circular principle. This statement is remarkable, given the role that wastes play in renewable energies. It is nevertheless a coherent position from the Circular Economy perspective: the main goal is to keep any raw material as long as possible within the life cycle, by finding ways to use it many times. Only when all use options as a material are exploited, the last option of energy recovery should be chosen. This last step is however not a step that creates a circular use in the economic system.

Energy use/recovery is of vital importance in the context of both the European forest-based industries and the energy sector: today approximately more than 300 million m³, that is 50% of the 600 million m³ annually roundwood resources from harvested trees, end up in energy use i.e., fuelwood. About 2/3 of this volume represents

fuelwood directly used for energy recovery, while 1/3 are rejects of production process (e.g., sawdust, wood scraps, cut-outs) that are in general also only considered for energy recovery³. These volumes account for about half of the European renewable energy production which represents about 20% of the entire EU energy mix⁴. In sum, wood provides about 10% of the total EU energy supply.

It is commonly acknowledged that a large portion of these wood resources are of sufficient medium to high quality so that they could potentially be used as raw material for various products with a significantly longer life cycle. This would allow for continuing to create both more economic value and more benefits for the climate than fuelwood use. However, this issue is at the core of the hot debate how to trade-off between use as a material on the one hand and the replacement of fossil fuels with higher climate impact on the other, because under the current conditions the woodworking industry faces substantial challenges to undertake the shift towards increased and prolonged material use.

The main reasons why under current market conditions this shift is difficult and not favoured by certain parties involved include:

- National subsidy schemes for renewable (bio)energy exist/have existed in many countries and have built up a large infrastructure over the last decades, including large incineration plants and a broad diffusion of small-scale bioenergy boilers for public and private use. These investments are the basis for the high share of wood energy in the EU energy mix. For companies, once these investments are accomplished, it makes little sense to then steer in a different direction.
- The woodworking industry requires substantial amounts of thermal and electric energy for their internal transformation and drying processes of the material. This can be generated directly on-site using energy conversion of production rejects (i.e., woodworking produces high volumes of cut-offs, sawdust, etc). Sawmills, panel producers and many other wood industries with production lines that run 24/7 rely a lot on their locally installed bioenergy systems, which replace a significant share of fossil energy sources.
- The waste wood market is another factor: waste regulations in many European countries, especially regarding construction and demolition waste, do not allow to reuse certain wood assortments that bear a risk of being polluted with harmful substances during the use phase (e.g., construction, packaging). Particleboard

³ Mantau 2015. Wood flow analysis: Quantification of resource potentials, cascades and carbon effects. Biomass and Bioenergy 79, 28-38. [sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0961953414003924](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0961953414003924) | UNECE-FAO 2017. Wood Energy in the ECE Region. unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/timber/publications/SP-42-Interactive.pdf

⁴ EUROSTAT 2018. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Gross_inland_consumption_of_renewable_energy,_EU-28,_2005_and_2016.png | EUROSTAT 2020 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/t2020_31/default/line?lang=en

producers treat, after the separation of the recyclable material fraction from the waste wood, the remaining unusable waste volumes in incineration power plants, recovering energy for their large factories⁵.

- The added value of the concerned material (production rejects) is relatively low. Cost efficient transportation is therefore limited and from the business perspective, energy recovery is often the better option.
- However, in many cases the energy production (recovery from production rejects) substantially exceeds the actual own energy needs of a plant, which means the surplus is sold to the market. Many woodworking industries have created a viable business from producing wood fuel (e.g., pellets). Major incineration plants in wood industries supply energy to local and/or national grids. Bioenergy has thus become a major income factor and an important part of their business model.
- Finally, as addressed under the R2-Rethink principle (chapter 2.2.2), the development of new products, new markets and new business models requires adequately trained staff and long-term strategies. These also require investments and taking risks that present a high challenge when compared to established energy recovery procedures.

2.2.11 Smart technologies

Digitalisation and industry 4.0 provide companies unique opportunities for innovation and knowledge-based production models, including smart factories, on-demand production and mass customization. The digitalisation has also become an enabling and disruptive driver for innovation in the wood industry. There has been tremendous progress for example in sensor and scanning technologies for wood and in automation for engineered wood products allowing for identifying the origins and monitoring products and materials in the use phase.

Such technology-based product and material traceability is one of the key enablers for establishing Circular Economy when it comes to closing material loops, managing smart value chains and waste streams, implementing challenging concepts such as cascade use, and finally assuring product quality for clients (e.g., sustainable sourcing, avoidance of pollutants, certification). Two innovative practices were identified:

- *RFIDdirect* (no. 5.1) smart wood tags using radio-frequency identification technology (RFID) are designed to be embedded in manufactured products.
- The *Galician Forest Administration's* wood products value chain tracing system FORTRA (no. 5.2) uses blockchain and QR-codes for tracking of timber and products from forest to customers.

⁵ Bioreg 2018. D1.1 European wood waste statistics report and model regions. <http://bioreg.eu>

3 Collecting innovative practices

3.1 Open Call to companies in the forest-based sector

3.1.1 Launch and communication of the call

Task 3.1 prepared a Europe-wide open call for innovative practices in SMEs and larger companies. The call guidelines defined the scope, selection criteria and evaluation procedure. The open call was split into a 1st and 2nd call round to be able to consider lessons learnt and to assure applications from a range of companies in terms of products and country distribution. The announcement and dissemination were realised jointly by InnovaWood and FCBA (cf. Annex 5.2).

The call was titled '*3W Factor – Wood you mind?*' (Wood processing, Wood reuse, Wood recycling). It was open to all kinds of wood companies in Europe, which were invited to present their success stories of readily implemented technical solutions or novel innovations for resource efficiency, reuse and recycling. The call targeted mainly SMEs in the sector, but its scope was open to all sorts of technological solutions, including typical process improvements (e.g., upgraded equipment, energy and mass flow management, recycling), to more advanced solutions (e.g., supply chain management, novel business models, digitalisation).

The open calls were announced and officially launched on September 3rd, 2019 (1st call) and on February 1st, 2021 (2nd call) on the project website woodcircus.eu and social media channels. The call text providing basic information on the call was prepared and circulated with the announcement through the partner networks. The call was communicated widely through the various channels already three months before each actual launch. It was also communicated during various events and conferences, where the project with support from stakeholders (i.e., EU/national associations).

The following means were used to communicate the open call (cf. Annex 5.1):

- *Website*: To announce the call, a dedicated page was created on the project website with a distinguishing banner and a countdown timer towards the launch date. This page was afterwards constantly updated through the launch and duration of the call to include all the relevant information concerning the call and related modalities.
- *Social media*: The call was communicated through social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn) and circulated in the partner networks on national, European and international levels. Several rounds of postings were made, forwarded and retweeted by partners and stakeholder organisations before, during and after the launch to gain visibility.

- *Leaflet*: The call was also promoted in different events using the project leaflet. It includes a brief description of the call with a QR code leading to the call webpage. Estimated 500+ copies of the leaflet have been distributed for relevant stakeholders during several project related events.
- *Call text*: The formal call text announcing and giving basic information on the call was circulated through targeted emailing and newsletters by the partners. It was also published on the project website and on social media. The call text presented the scope, selection criteria and evaluation procedure as well as the timeline.
- *Project factsheet*: In addition to the leaflet, a brief description of the call with the QR code was included to the project factsheet to gain visibility in various stakeholder events, which is also accessible via the project website.
- *Presentation*: A special open call presentation including basic information on the project and on the details of the call was used.

For the 1st call, the initial announced collection date was set to November 31st, 2019. The deadline was later extended to January 19th, 2020. For the 2nd call the announced latest collection date was set to March 15th 2021.

3.1.2 Submissions of participating companies

To participate in the open call, companies were asked to submit their application via an online form (cf. Annex 5.1.3). They were required to provide a short company profile and a description of their solution, including evidence for the savings potentials, efficiency gains and sustainability impacts. The proposal form for applications was accessible on the project website via a dedicated subpage.

In total, 29 companies with innovative practices from 15 countries were retained from both calls, i.e., 8 from the first call and 21 from the second call (Table 8). The received applications were reviewed by an international expert committee represented by members of the consortium. In the review meeting, the characteristics and innovative features of each company practice were discussed, and it was debated which outstanding aspects could be highlighted.

The applications revealed to be very relevant for Circular Economy, but they also turned out to be highly diverse. As they could barely be compared directly to each other, achieving a closer evaluation and ranking, which had initially been foreseen for this task, was limited. It was therefore decided to include and analyse all complete applications and describe them as snapshot showcases of the development towards Circular Economy in the wood sector. Each case was considered as valuable example, which provides insights and conclusions of interest, thus allowing target groups to identify with and be inspired by these innovative practices.

3.1.3 Factsheets created for dissemination

All application documents were collected and reviewed by InnovaWood. The applications were crosschecked internally for completeness and relevance before collecting further details and feedback from the companies.

Based on the material received from companies (e.g., filled application form, public websites, annual reports, photos, marketing material, etc), InnovaWood drafted factsheets using a common layout. The factsheets were further reviewed and approved by the consortium and the companies themselves. The factsheet format was chosen because it provides a condensed but easily understandable overview of the main features of the innovative product or solution. It highlights the key aspects both with visual pictures and short texts in concise info boxes (the reading time is a few minutes at maximum). In addition, the PDF factsheet includes contact details of the companies and additional weblinks to more information.

The factsheets are suitable communication means for raising interest and awareness for the topic of Circular Economy, equally targeting professionals in the sector but also the public. Individual factsheets can easily be shared via info portals and social media. They are good examples that can be included in presentations during online or offline events and meetings. The factsheets are also suited for educational purposes, e.g., as an introduction to Circular Economy innovation in the forest-based sector.

Through Europe-wide dissemination efforts of the project within the R&I community and the larger forest-based sector, and further sharing by network contacts and followers, the factsheets have reached a wide audience. The companies gained increased visibility beyond their own usual communication channels, and their innovative practices can become more known in the wood industry and other communities engaged with the Circular Economy.

3.1.4 Lessons learnt from the open call approach

The open call approach including the categorization can be considered a suitable method for both identifying key actors in a given sector and supporting them to promote and improve resource efficiency in SMEs. The specific company and product descriptions summarized on the factsheets create a common set of communication materials to which all companies and other stakeholders can easily refer to (per the weblink, the pdf file, and/or the printout version). The factsheets also proved to be suitable for use in webinars, physical conferences and education programs connected to Circular Economy and innovation.

The mentoring, recommendations for further improvement, documentation, and dissemination were offered to all applicants. In addition to the factsheet developed together with all 29 companies, four applicants were selected for a deeper individual LCA assessment including recommendations for improvement (cf. D5.2 final report).

Four companies participated directly in WoodCircus webinars and conferences as invited speakers and obtained feedback from the experts. During the review, the selected companies held direct discussions with the consortium experts about their Circular Economy and approaches and were introduced to other cases and stakeholders with similar interests. Finally, the analysis of their own activities being contextualised in the CSCE framework (cf. chapter 2.1) is an additional useful result.

The following chapter presents the collection of approved and published final factsheets. They are organised in groups of different wood-based product types. All final factsheets were published on the project website woodcircus.eu and in the *WoodCircus Good Practice Repository*⁶ on the EC OpenAIRE platform Zenodo.

⁶ WoodCircus repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/woodcircus/>

3.2 Final factsheet collection

3.2.1 Wood-based panels

Table 3 List of companies and innovative practices in wood-based panels

No.	Company logo	Innovative practice, company, country, factsheet link
1.1		National wood collection and recycling network Consorzio Rilegno, Italy https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788741
1.2		Particleboards made of recycled post-consumer wood Unilin Panels, Belgique https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788741
1.3		Fibre recovery process for wood fibre board recycling MDF Recovery Ltd, UK https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788915
1.4		Wood collection and recycling network for particle boards Egger Group, Romania https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788920
1.5		Wood fibre insulation panel assembly systems GUTEX H. Henselmann GmbH&Co.KG, Germany https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5789396
1.6		Precision measurement system to reduce material and energy use in wood panel production Fagus GreCon, Germany https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788739

Rilegno

National wood collection and recycling network

Italy's national consortium for the collection, recovery and recycling of wood packaging is a dynamic group of 2,000 companies, which transform wood, produce packaging, supply and import semi-finished packaging. The voluntary members include recycling companies, producers of boards, pulp, blocks, panels and pallets. The large network enables a competitive recycling market of up to 2 million tons of collected material annually.

Highlights of innovative features

- The collection network covers the entire territory with 419 private collection platforms serving the industrial and commercial sector.
- More than 4,500 municipalities representing over 42 million inhabitants have signed agreements for urban collection.
- 15 major panel producers recycle large volumes to supply board products to furniture and construction industries, amounting for about 3.2 million tons of released items.
- 63% of the material sent for recycling into boards comes mainly from wooden packaging such as pallets, crates for fruit and vegetables, boxes, cable reels, cork stoppers.
- In addition, 60 million items equal to 839,000 tons of regenerated pallets are returned to the market, which thus re-enter the logistics circuit instead of becoming waste.
- The gained CO₂ savings amount to around 1 million tons per year. The economic impact is around 1.4 million euros and 6,000 jobs.

The Rilegno network is a showcase of excellence in post-consumer wood waste and recycling logistics, maximizing the benefits of an integrated circular value chain and market approach for the entire wood and furniture sector.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #07 | 2021

Consorzio Rilegno

Via Luigi Negrelli 24A
47042 Cesenatico (FC)
Italy | rilegno.org

Unilin panels

Furniture boards produced from recovered wood

Post-consumer wood from urban areas is collected, cleaned and processed in high tech recycling plants to re-convert into viable raw material for quality board products for furniture and interior use.

Highlights of innovative features

- Large investments in high tech sorting and cleaning equipment enables the processing of huge volumes of demolition and urban waste: up to 1 million tons are recycled into panels per year.
- Chipboards are produced with up to 90% recycled wood.
- To offset carbon emissions, factories are powered 70-90% by renewable energy from wood waste that cannot be recycled.
- Partnerships with a large supplier network including container parks, demolition firms, packaging and furniture industries ensure the recovery of large wood volumes that are no longer usable for other processes.

UNILIN represents one of the most advanced recycling systems for valorizing post-consumer wood waste streams on large industrial scale. It relies on an established collection system and supplier network. Cascading wood reduces the need for fresh roundwood and prolongs the carbon capture. Particle boards from recovered wood are a prime case for Circular Economy in the sector.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #10 | 2021

UNILIN Panels
Ingelmunstersteenweg 229
B-8780 Oostrozebeke, Belgium

unilinpanels.com

MDF Recovery

Closed Loop Solution for the MDF Industry

Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) is found in every home, office, and retail environment. Despite its popularity, it is considered unrecyclable. MDF Recovery (MDFR) is a world-first technology economically recovering wood fibres from used MDF, creating a sustainable, low-cost, raw material.

Highlights of innovation features

- The MDRF recovery process is the first scalable approach to reclaim MDF board fibres from resin enabling their reuse as a raw material for the manufacturing of new boards.
- The process replaces the two most energy intensive stages of the manufacture of MDF from virgin timber, steaming and refining, therefore reducing the embedded CO₂ of the finished product.
- The recovered fibre is of the same high quality as virgin wood fibre and provides a feedstock to the manufacturers of MDF board, insulation products and formable packing materials.

Over 100 million m³ of MDF are produced each year across the globe. Around 20% is wasted during the manufacturing process and in the supply chain, not including post-consumer 'end-of-life' MDF, resulting in a huge potential market for MDRF's production of new recycled material that reduces pressure on standing forests.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #23 | 2021

MDF Recovery Ltd
United Kingdom

mdfrecovery.co.uk

EGGER Group

Cascading wood use

EGGER produces an extensive product range of wood-based materials based on chipboard, OSB, and MDF board, as well as timber.

Highlights of innovative features

- In Romania, EGGER commissioned both a recycling facility at the production plant and public waste wood collection points to enable local waste wood flows.
- The waste wood is shredded before transport to the production plant to reduce the number of transporting trucks.
- Instead of releasing emissions, around 3.1 tons of CO² are bound in each recycled ton of waste wood.
- The quantities of waste wood recycled by EGGER in Romania in 2019 replaced the potential use of approx. 65,900 ha of forest.

For the production of wood-based materials, EGGER invests in resource saving technology and uses not only primary but also secondary, i.e. recycled raw materials. Cascading wood reduces the need for fresh roundwood and prolongates the carbon capture. Using recycling material in the production of chipboards is a prime case for Circular Economy in the sector.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #24 | 2021

EGGER Group
Weiberndorf 20
6380 St. Johann in Tirol
AUSTRIA

egger.com

GUTEX

Eco-friendly wood fibre insulation panel systems

A leading brand of high-quality insulation products and systems for new build and renovation. The main raw materials are untreated wood residues that are supplied from byproducts of regional sawmills. During the production process, all residues are recycled internally.

Highlights of innovative features

- A complete portfolio of easy-to-install insulation solutions for all building compartments, including walls, roofs and window frames.
- Panels are fixed only mechanically and thus can be removed easily during the deconstruction phase. Clean materials can be separated and remain functional for potential reuse and for recycling.
- Panels are natureplus® certified, containing limited amount of binder (<4%). As a diffusion open natural material, they balance air humidity much better than petrol-based insulations and thus provide good air quality and a comfortable indoor climate.
- Standardized according to fire resistance class F90-B or REI 90.

Wood-based insulation products improve the ecological footprint of buildings in two ways: the enhanced thermal insulation reduces the heating energy demand, and the nature-based raw material substitutes conventional insulation based on fossil or energy-intensive products. Wood fibre insulation panels are long-lived products that can contribute decisively to transforming the building sector into a carbon sink.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #15 | 2021

GUTEX Holzfaserplattenwerk
H. Henselmann GmbH + Co KG
Gutenberg 5
D-79761 Waldshut-Tiengen

gutex.de/en

FORMATOR®

High material efficiency in wood panels through smart precision equipment

Wood panels are produced in a large-scale process where wood chips are sprayed on a continuous conveyor belt and compressed into boards. This smart mat spraying system uses sensors for precision measurements to reduce the weight per unit area without loss in panel quality.

Highlights of innovative features

- The precision system automatically controls the homogenisation of weight in the panel. Excess material is removed by finetuned scalper rolls and returned immediately into the process.
- Perfectly formed panels with the desired optimal mechanical properties of the final product can be produced. Customer-specific offsets can be realised with highest precision. Advanced detection of risk potentials such as metals or glue lumps is also included.
- Raw material savings can attain 2% or 16 kg/m³, which correspond to about 9.9 million kg per year in a typical MDF production line.

The system allows for large material and energy savings resulting from reduced use of wood, less glue, reduced energy demand, less waste, and less logistics cost due to lower panel weight.

The system ensures optimal use of the raw material in the panel product by avoiding production wastes and hence reduce pressure on forest resources.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #06 | 2021

Fagus-GreCon Greten GmbH & Co. KG
Hannoversche Strasse 58
31061 Alfeld, Germany
fagus-grecon.com

3.2.2 Furniture, interiors and other solid wood products

Table 4 List of companies and innovative practices in furniture and interiors

No.	Company logo	Innovative practice, company, country, factsheet link
2.1		Design furniture using upcycled materials by Green Furniture Concept, Sweden https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788765
2.2		National professional furniture reuse and recycling network by Valdelia, France https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788824
2.3		Furniture revalorising local recovered wood by Holy wood asbl, Belgium https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788728
2.4		Circular furniture made of recovered wood by HERSO, Netherlands https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788947
2.5		Solid wooden doors made of recovered wood by Melu d.o.o., Slovenia https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788713
2.6		Large-span windows made of recovered wood by M SORA, Slovenia https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788709
2.7		Circular wooden windows by WEBO, Netherlands https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788769
2.8		Modular furniture made of recycled materials by Donar d.o.o., Slovenia https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788909
2.9		Oak lamellas for flooring by Zunami LLC, Ukraine https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788955

Green Furniture concept

Sustainable design for public interior areas

Seamless, winding and wooden public furniture and lamps improving interior acoustics based on 4 cornerstones : Chemical Awareness, Design & Resources, Reforestation and Post Sales Responsibility

Highlights of innovative features

- The furniture is highly configurable and adaptable to users needs.
- Building Information Modelling BIM data are provided to architects for an easy handling when choosing products for projects.
- The use of up- and recycled raw materials includes steel, aluminium and ocean plastic.
- Product-as-a-Service business models, leasing and buyback conditions foster the circularity of the products.
- For every furniture sold a tree is planted.

Seamless' Seating means room for more people when needed and the possibility of designing grand furniture configurations in scale with large spaces. Configurations that can take any creative formation, follow the lines of the building and lead the flow of people. 'Acoustic Lighting' means lighting designed to provide outstanding visual and acoustic spheres. 'Sustainable' is our story.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #11 | 2021

GREEN
FURNITURE
CONCEPT

Green Furniture concept
Carlsgatan 3,
21120 Malmö, Sweden

greenfc.com

Valdelia

Closing the loop in the second life furniture market

Financed through an environmental contribution as part of furniture producers' extended product responsibility, Valdelia recuperates used professional furniture and closes the loop in four ways: second hand, re-use, upcycling and material recycling.

Highlights of innovative features

- Valdelia is a non-profit environmental organization with a national collection network connecting 1,200 members including manufacturers, distributors and importers on the regional and local level.
- Around 100,000 tons of used furniture are collected annually across the whole French territory, which of 3,000 tons are reused or enter an upcycling process.
- Many of the furniture upcycling initiatives also provide local jobs including social reintegration concepts.

Valdelia's innovation department has a twofold mission:

1) to explore innovative technical + organisational solutions to develop second life in the professional furniture sector.

2) to support the sector's players in applying these solutions to their manufacturing and distribution models as well as promoting eco-design and extending the life of products.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #16 | 2021

Valdelia
GARANTIR LA SECONDE VIE DES PRODUITS

Valdelia
ZAC de l' Hers
93 rue du Lac
31670 Labege, France

valdelia.org

Holy wood

Furniture valorising locally recovered waste wood

In a micro-value chain approach, old furniture and solid wood pieces are collected locally, dismantled and recovered so that it can be reused in new furniture. A cooperative association of designers and joiners creates a brand for unique, designed furniture pieces, appreciated by clients for their authentic touch of recycled wooden material.

Highlights of innovative features

- An abundant waste stream becomes a raw material for valuable products: The furniture is made by 85-100% of recovered wood!
- The furniture is handmade and created either in small series or as single projects corresponding to the clients' needs, giving them an individual, personalized character.
- The association supports solidarity as the old furniture is obtained mainly from the Emmaüs social cooperative that acts against poverty and exclusion.

Old wooden furniture that cannot be sold any more and would otherwise be incinerated is coming to a second life and re-circulated to local use. Upcycling of old furniture into individual furniture pieces for private homes, offices and public cultural spaces helps to create awareness for local raw material collection and valorization.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #04 | 2021

Hollywood asbl
63, rue du Fisch Club
7000 Mons, Belgium
holy-wood.be

Herso circular woodworks

Circular furniture and interiors without waste

Recovered wood material is remanufactured into beautiful designs for furniture, floors and interiors that have a unique character and valorise the vivid nature of wood surfaces and colours in long-lived products.

Highlights of innovative features

- With an own collection network, the company recovers wood supply from municipal waste and recycling centres.
- Clients can choose from design patterns that are created through assembly of different recovered wood origins.
- 'No waste' is used as brand for floors and interior walls, which are a reuse option also for demolition waste wood.
- Products are already labelled 'FSC Recycled' and an Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for architects is being developed.
- Versatile products which value respect for natural resources.

Recovered wood that is manufactured into valuable products revalorizes the natural material wood. Durable quality furniture is one of the best options to prolong the carbon storage of materials that are usually discarded. Circular brands by SMEs help to raise public awareness for the Circular Economy.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #26 | 2021

HERSO circular woodworkers
Molenhoeven 3
5472 PX Loosbroek
The Netherlands

herso.nl

Melu doors

Solid wooden doors using recovered wood

Wood materials are recovered from old doors and old wooden constructions to be reused as core for new, custom-made solid wooden doors with a unique design. The product portfolio includes also specialized folding doors, sliding doors, windbreaks and wall coverings.

Highlights of innovative features

- Solid doors are unique manufactured pieces for customers who value natural materials, strength and beauty in their homes.
- Custom-made design achieves high quality products with a long lifetime and valorizes the natural material wood.

Recovered wood material valorization in high-end products gives them a second life, as they would otherwise be considered waste. They substitute non-renewable materials and prolong the carbon storage impact of these products. Use of recycled materials in customized products helps to raise awareness for Circular Economy among end users.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #02 | 2021

Melu d.o.o.
3334 Luče ob Savinji
Slovenia
melu.si

TREE2U

Windows with increased dimensions using recovered wood

Circular design approach applied to wooden windows combines tradition and modern high tech to create distinct superior quality and long-life products.

Highlights of innovative features

- Recovered wood from characteristic historical building structures such as barns, mills, sheds, homesteads or hayracks is recycled into a modern, high-value product. Up to 30% recovery of wood from old structures can be achieved.
- Wood scantlings are complemented with a patented reinforcement system to redistribute load stress, enabling increased window dimensions of large span widths and up to 7m of height.
- Unique patina of reused wood can be used to add special and extraordinary identity and aesthetic value to the window product.
- Modular design approach and embedded smart sensors can prevent decay and prolong product life span.
- The company is developing a social app to improve wood recovery, by allowing users to send photos of excess or waste wood through the app allowing the company to decide if they will collect it.

The product helps raise consumer awareness for circular use in buildings. Large and slender windows optimize light transmission into built objects. Motorized windows integrate well into smart homes and can significantly enhance comfort and usability. The product is a prime example for a high-end circular and long-life product.

Company | Ownership of innovation

M Sora d.d.
Trg Svobode 2
4226 Žiri, Slovenia
m-sora.si

Factsheet #01 | 2021

Acknowledgements

M Sora took part in the EU co-funded projects: CaReWood, RecAPpture, TIGR4smart, ReWin, WOOLF

WEBO

Circular wooden windows with low maintenance

Wooden window frames, facade elements, BIM design or unique wood solutions. WEBO focuses on circular design, integration of recycled materials and modularity for easy replacements

Highlights of innovative features

- The outside window parts are made of chemically modified wood that allows for very low maintenance.
- The modularity of the window frame allows for exchanging only parts of the window if necessary.
- The interior part of the window frame is made of recycled or sustainably sourced wood.

Modular window frames allow for combining high performance modified wood on the outside and well insulating wood for the inner parts of the frame

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #12 | 2021

WEBO
Spoelerstraat 15,
7462 RW, Rijssen
The Netherlands

webo.nl

Donar

Ecodesign for sustainable furniture

Donar focusses on environmental awareness, social impact and customer education through user experience by producing modular recycled and recyclable furniture

Highlights of innovative features

- The shell of the chair is made of felt produced of recycled plastic bottles.
- It is a modular furniture allowing for easy recycling and replacement of all parts.
- A product-service business model reduces the environmental impact and helps closing the material loop.

Donar has created NicoLess, a simple but unique chair made of recycled felt (60% recycled PP bottles and 40% non-woven textile) and designed by Primož Jeza Studio. No extra glue or binders are added. The shell and the metal base are linked with straps and can be combined in compositions of various lengths or stored in vertical stacks facilitating

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #20 | 2021

DONAR d.o.o.
Gosposvetska 10
1000 Ljubljana
Slovenia

donar.si

Zunami LLC

Oak lamellas and pellets

Producer of high-quality oak lamellas for flooring and fuel pellets from production rejects focusing on efficiency increase and waste management

Highlights of innovative features

- Large investments in high tech planning, slicing equipment and patented drying systems connecting the production processes allowed to increase the material yield of oak lamellas by 20%.
- Complete utilization of wood processing waste, including bark and sawdust, the Ukrainian company meets production standards of the leading of European woodworking enterprises
- The investments into higher process efficiency and optimized pellet production allowed for reducing production waste by 35% corresponding to the volume of 6.000 trees per year.

The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (ERBD) supported Zunami in their efforts for more efficient and energy saving production processes through the FINTECC (Finance and Technology Transfer Centre for Climate Change) that is part of the EBRD's contribution towards climate technology transfer to countries in transition

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #28 | 2021

Zunami LLC
48 A Selyanska
45100 Rozhyshe
Ukraine

zunami.com.ua

3.2.3 Wood construction

Table 5 List of companies and innovative practices in wood construction

No.	Company logo	Innovative practice, company, country, factsheet link
3.1		Building system for houses using wooden pallets by SOFRINNOV, France https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788802
3.2		Glue free, load-bearing ceilings for high acoustic demand by Tschopp Holzbau AG, Switzerland https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788719
3.3		Wave Layered Timber building system by Aalto Haitek Oy, Finland https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788734
3.4		Timber-hybrid building design system by CREE GmbH, Austria https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788781
3.5		Cross Laminated Timber construction elements by Lignotrend, Germany https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5792555
3.6		High strength timber for constructions by Fagus Suisse SA, Switzerland https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788928
3.7		Fast assembly wood construction system by Termowood, Norway https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788953

SOFRINNOV

Ecological construction recycled and recyclable

A combination of used wood pallets and Lego-like connectors called SYCLAT® allows for very simple and setup of shelter and leisure houses. The houses are completely reversible and recyclable and can be used as short-time and low budget accommodation or be equipped with more durable wall insulation and roofing.

Highlights of innovative features

- The walls of the construction are made from used pallets that are joined with SYCLAT® Lego-like connectors. Each pallet increasing the wall size by 1m² within seconds, allows for very fast construction.
- The system being very simple, no significant training nor machines other than a cordless screwdriver are needed.
- The constructions are suitable for leisure and temporary accommodation or offices in a price range of €500 to €850 per m².
- If used inside existing buildings (e.g. production halls, trade fairs, office spaces) the price range drops to €150 to €350 per m².

Simple but highly effective constructive measures prevent the wood from getting wet through water stagnation or capillary effects (e.g. used tire chunks as separators). In this way, the wood remains sufficiently dry to exclude attacks of wood decaying fungi.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #14 | 2021

SOFRINNOV
40 Chemin de Lasbadorques
31700 Cornebarrieu
FRANCE

BRESTA® Acoustic Gentle

Load-bearing ceiling element suited for high acoustic demand

The timber elements have integrated wood fibre boards for optimal sound absorption. Manufactured with a special CNC machine, the elements are assembled using glue-free wooden dowel connections.

Highlights of innovative features

- The elements meet the requirements of statics, room acoustics, sound insulation and fire protection in one product.
- In contrast to conventional acoustic ceilings with the same high performance, the sound absorption of this product is integrated into the static load-bearing element.
- Filigree optics enable a modern, contemporary architecture.
- The element can be further customized through inlay panels to increase fire safety levels or optimize room acoustics.

Improved indoor acoustics of buildings increase the quality-of-life in private, professional, public and educational spaces. They enhance attentiveness, performance, concentration and ability to learn. The product is leading example for high acoustic performance through constructive circular design in wood.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #03 | 2021

Tschopp Holzbau AG
6280 Hochdorf
Switzerland
tschopp-holzbau.ch

WLT® Wave Layered Timber

Glue-free mass timber for aesthetic structures

This innovative construction technology from Finland focusses on simplicity and flexibility: the concept is a universal mass timber building component for every type of construction that can be manufactured with basic technical skills using different types of wood.

Highlights of innovative features

- This special wave profile joining technique creates homogenous, crack-free tight structures with high dimensional strength. The material reacts to ambient moisture changes by natural optimisation of tensions. It suits various wood species, including recycled wood.

- It is a highly versatile, cost-efficient building system: The structurally strong, light-weight material enables demanding structural shapes.
- It has a short lead, production and construction time.
- It can easily be modified, disassembled and transported for re-use.
- It is glue and additive free and thus ecologically harmless, fully recyclable with zero waste.

WLT® makes practical and beautiful solutions possible even under demanding conditions or logistical restrictions. The assembly demands little training and no special equipment.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Aalto Haitek Oy
Juustotie 2
69300 Toholampi, Finland
aaltohaitek.fi

Factsheet #05 | 2021

CREE Timber-Hybrid System

Versatile prefabricated building construction

A sophisticated hybrid construction system for high rise buildings, connecting modular prefabricated components to an optimized planning and construction process in a constantly evolving collaborative model. A cutting-edge solution for the new digital era.

Highlights of innovative features

- The modular system uses a predefined grid of prefabricated hybrid slab panels to which the various other components - walls, ceilings, facades, etc. - are added with large flexibility of the layout.
- Based on a full digital twin, the integrated planning and delivery allows to optimize all flows of materials, information and processes. This leads to tremendous potential savings on cost, transport, material, time and carbon emissions.
- Open functional spaces with a biophilic atmosphere provide a healthy office environment for well-being of employees.
- Life Cycle Management ensures highly energy efficient buildings.

Next generation buildings require flexibility and full control over the entire life cycle from construction, operation and end-of-life. Integrating all phases into digital collaboration models delivers the future of aesthetics and performance in building design.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #13 | 2021

CREE
BUILDINGS

CREE GmbH
Färbergasse 17b
6850 Dornbirn | Austria

creebuildings.com

Lignotrend

LIGNO® Cross Laminated Timber

High-quality timber construction elements for floor, roof and wall structures as well as for use in interior finishing with focus on architectural design, individual configurability and room acoustics.

Highlights of innovative features

- Lignotrend's cross laminated timber CLT components reduce wood consumption by their internal web structure.
- All construction elements are natureplus® certified guaranteeing both high indoor air quality and the fulfilment of all sustainability criteria.
- Lignotrend focuses on providing products with genuine wood surface. A specialty is the locally sourced silver fir which is processed as a knotless surface that allows for unique interior design.

As a pioneer in cross laminated timber, Lignotrend design their products to be individually configured. This allows to meet more typical requirements of building at once than only load-bearing: The products are characterised by intelligent multifunctionality.

Architectural design, sound insulation, room acoustics and increased fire resistance, are examples of disciplines that can be addressed by modification of the elements' internal structure.

Configuration goes with cost-effectiveness for the respective construction task and caters precisely to the planners' specification and design ideas.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #22 | 2021

LIGNO TREND®

Lignotrend
Landstrasse 25
79809 Weilheim
Germany

lignotrend.com

FAGUS BAUHOLZ

Swiss made high strength structural timber

Beech hardwood lamellas are processed into high performance glued laminated timber providing constructive elements for high mechanical load applications such as wide span roofs and multi-storey buildings.

Highlights of innovative features

- Beech wood is abundant in Swiss forests, but so far it is poorly valorized and large volumes end up directly in bioenergy use. This product converts such raw material instead into a high-end use.
- FAGUS structural timber has 2x higher bending and tensile strength and 3x higher compression and shear strength compared to conventional softwood glulam.
- It enables extended spans and slender construction elements with less timber volume. The single beam maximal dimensions are 0.28 x 1.24 x 13.5m.
- It replaces energy intensive products such as steel and concrete and provides long-term carbon storage in buildings.
- Production rejects are used for manufacturing of solid wood furniture panels and other products.

 Swiss Confederation
 Innosuisse – Swiss Innovation Agency

For architects and planners, the high-performance beech wood is a pioneer building product, because it allows for more filigree designs offering new aesthetic and constructive possibilities.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet # 25 | 2021

FAGUS
SUISSE

Fagus Suisse SA
Grand'Rue 21
2345 Les Breuleux
Switzerland

fagussuisse.ch
fagusbauholz.ch

Termowood

Tewo wood building system

This building system relies on relatively small and light building elements that are plugged and screwed together on the construction site without heavy machinery

Highlights of innovative features

- The Tewo building concept allows for fast assembly and minimal waste on the construction site.
- The simplicity of the system allows for coupling high quality and well insulated buildings with affordable construction costs.
- The Tewo-Flex system is a variant providing flexible and reusable inner walls for office buildings and similar applications.
- Tewo can be used in Building Information and Modelling (BIM) applications.

Tewo constructions are based on structural wall elements consisting of two cross-laminated plywood layers separated by insulation material and joined together with wooden dowels. The elements are prefabricated and arrive ready to be assembled on the construction site. The company is active in Norway, Denmark, the Netherlands, UK and USA.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #27 | 2021

Termowood AS
Høversjøvegen 49
2090 Hurdal, Norway

tewo.no

3.2.4 Special products and sidestream uses

Table 6 List of companies and innovative practices in special wood products

No.	Company logo	Innovative practice, company, country, factsheet link
4.1		Wooden nails for timber constructions by Raimund Beck AG, Germany https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788833
4.2		Wood flour and fibres for high added value applications by Holzmühle Westerkamp, Germany https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788967
4.3		Plant-based plastic alternatives by Orineo BV, Belgium https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5792551
4.4		Ultra-durable modified wood Accoya brand by Accsys Technologies, Netherlands https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788849
4.5		Furniture and constructions made of recovered of wooden mussle farm rafts by Fearmaga, Spain https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788827

Raimund Beck KG

LignoLoc® wooden nail system

LignoLoc® nails are made of densified European beech wood. They can be applied pneumatically without predrilling or application of glue.

Highlights of innovative features

- Featuring a warm, natural esthetic, this ecological fastener also offers excellent corrosion resistance, perfect insulation, and can easily be cut and machined without damaging processing equipment.
- LignoLoc® is the most sustainable professional fastening system on the market with more than 70 % lower CO2 emission vs. conventional systems.
- No additional labor costs because predrilling or glue are not needed.
- Also available soon with head for exterior applications.

The heat from the penetration process causes a chemo-mechanical reaction between nail and penetrated wood “locking” them together. LignoLoc® nails can be driven into solid structural timber with the Fasco® pneumatic nailer. With the official approval of the DIBt in 2020, Lignoloc® nails are allowed for use in load bearing shear wall constructions.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #18 | 2021

Raimund Beck KG
Raimund-Beck-Strasse 1,
5270 Mauerkirchen
Austria

beck-lignoloc.com

Holzmühle Westerkamp

Wood flour and fibres

The producer of high-quality wood flour, wood fibres, wood granulate and lignocellulose provides a source material for high added value applications in the food and feed industry and for the manufacturing of a diverse set of biobased products.

Highlights of innovative features

- The company is working according to a strict product quality standard needed to supply their main market the food and feed industry with feed mixes and litter material.
- Applications also include the production of compostable or non-compostable biobased products such as wood plastic composites.
- Due to the high-quality of wood flours needed in the feed and food industry, the lignocellulose can also be used in high-end processes such as filtration of glucose, starch, oil and used fats.
- Used plant-based fats can be cleaned to produce biodiesel while the remaining filter cake can be used for heat or energy production.

Lignocellulose is the source material for various products and is made from wood milled to a homogenous material reaching from flour up to coarser particles. Holzmühle Westerkamp constantly develops new tailor-made products in close cooperation with their clients to satisfy their needs and explore new markets.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #29 | 2021

Holzmühle Westerkamp GmbH
Norddöhlen 31
49429 Visbek,
Germany

westerkamp-gmbh.de

Orineo

Plant-based plastic alternatives

Orineo creates bio-based binding agents and durable plant-based materials for replacing fossil-based products and allowing for cradle-to-cradle material-loops

Highlights of innovative features

- OriBond is a 100% plant-based 2-component thermosetting system derived from non-toxic ingredients and contains 65% non-food crop ingredients, 25% agricultural waste and 10% beet sugar derivate.
- OriBond can be used as binder in metal coating, agglomeration of granules and particles such as wood or cork and production of high-pressure laminate boards (HPL).
- In the production of wood-based panels, OriBond replaces formaldehyde and leads to water resistant boards.

A wood panel made with OriBond is 100% based on renewable resources. Therefore, it is entirely part of the carbon cycle, ideal for a Cradle-to-Cradle approach. Used panels can be reprocessed into new panels. At the end of the commercial lifecycle, if not reused, the product will not introduce toxic or persistent compounds into the environment.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #21 | 2021

ORINEO BV
Acaciastraat 14, 3071
Erps – Kwerps, Belgium

orineo.com

Accsys Technologies

Ultra-durable modified wood

Accsys produces Accoya® wood: a sustainable, stable and durable modified wood to support the built environment and help tackle the embodied carbon challenge.

Highlights of innovative features:

- A proprietary acetylation process reduces the ability of the wood to absorb water, making it more dimensionally stable and no longer attractive to wood decaying fungi and insects.
- Accoya® provides a 25-year warranty in ground or freshwater and 50 year above ground.
- Accoya® wood is Cradle to Cradle Certified™ Gold and therefore suitable for Circular Economy business models.

As every piece of Accoya® wood has been modified through to its core, it provides the same performance no matter how the wood is cut, planed, drilled or shaped. Accoya® wood is durability class 1 and is ideal for many applications including window frames, doors, façades, cladding, decking, all without the use of preservatives.

Accoya® wood decking Venlo City Hall, the Netherlands

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #19 | 2021

accoya

Accsys Technologies
Postbus 2147, 6802 CC Arnhem
The Netherlands

accoya.com

Accoya®, is a registered trademark owned by Titan Wood Limited, a wholly owned subsidiary of Accsys Technologies PLC, and may not be used or reproduced without written permission.

Fearmaga

Federation of Sawmills and Timber Finishers

Fearmaga is a non-profit sector organization that defends the interests of small and medium-sized timber companies in Galicia, Spain. They promote the recycling of mussel farms after 25 years of use on the sea.

Highlights of innovative features

- The mussel farms, 20x20m rafts of bare eucalyptus beams, create substantial added value and sequester carbon for 25 years floating on the sea.
- These rough conditions create a very sought-after surface aspect of the beams that are delicately recovered to create high added value furniture in the 2nd use period of the wood.
- The long life-cycle of these products connects local SME based value chains and therefore contributes to social cohesion and cultural identity.

In Galicia, the wood industry is closely connected to the sea industry. “MareMonte” is a documentary high-lighting this connection on the example of the life cycle of eucalyptus beams from rafts of mussel farms to a new use as beams in construction or rehabilitation, interior design, hotel and garden furniture, fences and gates.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #17 | 2021

Fearmaga
Rua de Amio 114, 15707
Santiago de Compostela, Galicia

maderasdegalicia.com

3.2.5 Smart tools

Table 7 List of companies and innovative practices in smart tools

No.	Company logo	Innovative practice, company, country, factsheet link
5.1	RFID direct [®] <small>www.RFIDdirect.co.uk</small>	RFID tags for material and product tracking by RFIDdirect Ltd, UK https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788749
5.2	XUNTA DE GALICIA	Wood products traceability tool by the Galician Forest Administration, Spain https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5788757

RFID Smart Wood

Tracing wood items with embedded RFID tags

A passive UHF chip-set is embedded in wood to enable traceability of any individual item in a manufacturing process and during the lifetime of a timber product. Traceability enables digital solutions for transparent circular value chains.

Highlights of innovative features

- The RFID Smart Wood tag is designed to offset the negative components and properties when embedded in wood. It resists physical damage that may occur as a result of swelling and shrinkage.
- It solves backscatter frequency issues related to wood properties, external factors, and ageing factors.
- Registered identification contained in the RFID tag allows to record full history and use or location of any object or asset.

RFID traceability tools can bring automation in wood industries to the next level of the 'Smart factory'. The possibilities include full real time data control across the factory, warehouse management, reverse traceability of products, reverse product engineering, and thus inspection mechanisms such as certification.

Company | Ownership of innovation

RFIDdirect Ltd
Bromfield Commercial Park
Mold, Flintshire
North Wales CH7 1HE, UK
RFIDdirect.eu

Germany Office
TZ Kleve
Boschstraße 16
47533 Kleve, Germany
RFIDdirect.de

Factsheet #08 | 2021

Patent application
19159901.8 – 1202

Galician Forest Administration

Wood products value chain tracing

FORTRA is a QR-code product label allowing consumers to access information on a wooden product including carbon footprint and the forests of origin

Highlights of innovative features

- Valorization of sustainable wooden products through increase of transparency and decision support for customers.
- The transparency is guaranteed through blockchain technology.
- The FORTRA tool is available in English, Spanish and Galician and could easily be extended to other languages and countries.
- The tool may be further expanded into the entire life-cycle of the product (repair, reuse, refurbish, recycle) fostering a circular bioeconomy in the region.

The final product displays a QR-code through which the customer accesses product information including manufacturing company, location of the forest of origin, cutting license and application date, wood volume used for the product, certification stamp, carbon footprint, regeneration after felling and all process operations of the transformation into the final product.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #9 | 2021

Galician Forest Administration
Rua de San Caetano, s/n,
75704 Santiago de Compostela
Spain

4 Conclusions

4.1 The role of wood products in the transformation to the Circular Economy paradigm

Building the foundation for the Circular Economy is one of the cornerstones of the *EU Green Deal*⁷, Europe's prime policy agenda for the transformation of the economy to a sustainable model. The *Circular Economy Action Plan*⁸ paves the road to reduce pressure on natural resources, to create sustainable growth and jobs while being a prerequisite to achieve the EU's 2050 climate neutrality target⁹. For the business sector, the transformation to Circular Economy means potentially large market opportunities, but also disruptive challenges in production and customer relations.

In the new circular paradigm, resources and products become interchangeable, and companies gain access to a huge secondary resource base, which is already in use but can easily be reconverted for the same purpose or a new function. This shift reduces and eliminates the need to access primary resources as main feed into the economic system. Secondly, producers are enabled to actively manage their 'stock' of products in use by their clients, applying advanced digital tools, and giving them better control over quality and quantity of their resources. Companies that achieve this paradigm shift in their business model will gain a clear competitive advantage.

Building with wood including renovation is seen as a major emerging market with a high potential for long-lived, circular products using nature-based materials, notably wood. Europe's growing need for housing leads to a large demand for materials for construction, renovation and interiors. It has been identified as an important sector in many EU policy strategies, i.e. the *Bioeconomy Strategy*¹⁰, the *EU Green Deal*⁷, the *Circular Economy Action Plan*⁸, the *Renovation Wave*¹¹, and the *New EU Forest Strategy*¹². The *New European Bauhaus*¹³ has launched a co-creative movement to design sustainable ways of living, linking architecture, civil engineering, art and culture, social inclusion and urban development, and will further accelerate research and innovation in circular construction materials and nature-based solutions.

⁷ EC 2019. A European Green Deal.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁸ EC 2021. Circular economy action plan.

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

⁹ EC. Climate action 2050 long-term strategy.

https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/strategies/2050_en

¹⁰ EC 2018. A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe. <https://op.europa.eu/s/s81X>

¹¹ EC 2020. A Renovation Wave for Europe - greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives. COM(2020) 662 final. eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0662

¹² EC 2021. New EU Forest Strategy for 2030. COM(2021) 572 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0572>

¹³ EC 2020. Beautiful, sustainable, together: the New European Bauhaus.

https://europa.eu/new-european-bauhaus/index_en

Figure 3 Forest-based sector material flows: opportunities for circularity¹⁴

Exploiting the climate positive effects of wood-based products will be key to meeting the climate targets for decreasing CO₂ emissions by industry. In connection with sustainable forest management, wood products have a trifold impact on climate change mitigation (3S): i) *sequestration* i.e. carbon capture of atmospheric CO₂ by forest trees in woody biomass, ii) *storage* in long-lived engineered wood products, and iii) *substitution* of carbon-intensive materials such as plastics, steel, cement or concrete. The decisive advantage of the nature-based material wood from the Circular Economy point of view is that it can be recycled both in the biological and technological cycle, and that the carbon storage time in products can be prolonged through additional reuse and recycling phases.

In this context, wood products (Figure 3) are now acknowledged more and more as climate friendly, sustainable solutions for building (new built and retrofitting), furniture and interiors (flooring, doors, stairs, windows, etc.), and also in a range of innovative applications (e.g., textiles, bioplastics, other biobased products). Wood products can play a major role in the decarbonization of major sectors and industries (e.g., the building and construction sector alone is responsible for circa 40% of total emissions, the textile and fashion sector for circa 10%). Already today, the EU forest-

¹⁴ Obucina M, Kuzman M, Sandberg D., 2017. Use of Sustainable Wood Building Materials in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Slovenia and Sweden. University of Sarajevo, Department Wood Technology. 112p. diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1140697/FULLTEXT01.pdf

based sector makes a positive climate contribution considering sequestration, storage and substitution that is equivalent to 20% of current EU fossil emissions¹⁵.

An essential factor for such large-scale transformation initiatives targeting whole sectors, urban centres and rural areas will be fully reusable products and recyclable materials, fit for adding value to circular use according to the 9R principles. To be adopted across all concerned sectors, these solutions will require widespread dissemination and exploitation, because the ultimate goal is to reduce the consumption of primary resources and to reverse fossil emissions.

4.2 Innovations demonstrating circular business practices in the forest-based industries

The 29 innovative practices provide a convincing set of examples of circular approaches of SMEs and larger companies, representing different product categories along the wood value chain, with emphasis on construction and furniture. The various innovative approaches illustrate that the adoption of Circular Economy concepts is well under way in the forest-based sector, but that there is still a long way until they can become the mainstream practice. Main lessons learnt and conclusions include:

- The 9R of the CSCE are particularly suitable for describing innovative practices, because they are comprehensive and at the same time sufficiently exhaustive to depict important aspects and details. Especially they allow to compare different products and practices in view of their circular business strategies.
- Company-level solutions such as the identified practices are essential for the future development of holistic circular value-added networks where material loops can be closed and residues and products in the use cycle can be either directly reused or fed back into the production – avoiding or minimizing incineration or landfill. Because huge amounts of resources are currently still wasted or used inefficiently, companies in the wood sector need to learn from such good practices and adopt innovative circular solutions on a larger scale.
- The hierarchy of the 9R permits to order practices regarding their level/impact of circularity. It highlights especially the need to implement more effective reuse options that maintain as much as possible the product or its components intact. In the current linear economy thinking, market actors are too often 'misled' to choose material reuse/recycling as a first option to 'save' resources. Such measures are widespread, because they can be implemented with comparatively little effort (e.g., adding a recycling bin for separating waste flows). In reality, they often might not leverage a high potential for better efficiency or lower environmental burden. In general, it is just not the right order of priority, which can be clearly illustrated to companies with the 9R-principles.

¹⁵ Holmgren P, 2020. Climate effects of the forest-based sector in the European Union. Study for CEPI. 25 pages. cepi.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Cepi_-study.pdf

- For closing the material loops, network organisations and major market actors (e.g., larger panel producers) can play a key role because they have the capacity to reach a critical mass of other market actors and leverage benefits all along a value chain. Such waste collection and supplier networks can be organized by one company alone (e.g., Unilin, Egger), or grow even into sizeable national schemes involving multiple producers and manufacturers (e.g., Rilegno, Valdelia).
- Wood is de facto today one of the main key resources for renewable energy supply in Europe. Energy generation from wood residues and wastes but also from virgin wood is widely established, supported by subsidies and technology diffusion. Individual producers and the sector as a whole are confronted with a trade-off that considerably impedes the progressive development of more circular solutions and value-added networks towards increased material recovery and side stream valorisation. To re-establish a level playing field in the sector, regulatory actions to prioritise product and material use and reuse over energy generation (e.g. the cascade principle) are urgently needed.
- Increasing the circularity of wood products is therefore an essential step and a new opportunity, as consumers begin to choose not only on price and performance, but also on environmental impact. Tested solutions that generate added value from recovered by-products can effectively reduce the need of virgin material and stimulate minimising the incineration of reusable wood. These approaches need to gain a much larger scale in the market.
- The outcomes will ultimately lead to an increased environmental performance of the whole chain, strengthening new pathways for circular, cascading use within the sector and enlarging the carbon storage life cycle impact of new recycled, engineered products. This has immediate benefits for the environment and health protection, and facilitates growth of furniture and construction markets towards safer living environments and sustainable cities contributing to the well-being of European citizens, and to the reduction of carbon emissions.
- Furthermore, once circular solutions will have entered the market, consumers will gain a larger choice on renewable products with lower footprints. Citizens will thereby increase their trust in green products made of sustainably sourced, recycled raw materials from domestic production in the EU, benefitting furthermore a higher self-sufficiency and autarky of raw material supply.
- Policy-driven prioritizations that aim at resource re-allocation to circular network development can play a decisive role: the successful example of an environmental contribution, implemented since 2012 by Valdelia in the French professional furniture sector, shows how a form of an eco-tax as part of the producers' extended product responsibility can lead the way to more circular furniture chains. However, such measures need to be tailor-made and balanced to prevent potentially counterproductive market distortions.

5 Annex

5.1 Open call outcomes

5.1.1 List of selected companies

Table 8 List of companies and innovative practices retained in the open call

No.	Company, Country	Summary title of proposed innovative practice
FIRST OPEN CALL		
1	M SORA, SI*	TREESU windows made of recovered wood from old buildings
2	Melu, SI	Doors made of recovered wood
3	Tschopp Holzbau AG, CH	BRESTA glue free, load-bearing ceilings for high acoustic demand
4	Holy wood, BE	Furniture made of recovered wood
5	Aalto Haitek Oy, FI*	Wave Layered Timber building system
6	Fagus GreCon, DE	Formator precision measurement system to reduce material and energy use in wood panel production
7	Consorzio Rilegno, IT*	National wood collection and recycling network
8	RFIDirect Ltd, UK	RFID Smart Wood tags for material and product tracking with embedded passive UHF chips
SECOND OPEN CALL		
9	Galician Forest Administration, SP	FORTRA tool for wood products value chain tracing
10	Unilin Panels, BE*	Particleboards made of recycled post-consumer wood
11	Green Furniture Concept, SE	Furniture for large public spaces using natural and upcycled materials
12	WEBO, NL	Circular wooden windows
13	CREE GmbH, AT	CREE timber-hybrid building design system
14	Sofrinno, FR	SYLCAT building system for houses made from wooden pallets
15	GUTEX H. Henselmann GmbH&Co.KG, DE	Wood fibre insulation panel assembly systems
16	Valdelia, FR	National professional furniture reuse and recycling network recycling network

No.	Company, Country	Summary title of proposed innovative practice
17	Fearmaga, SP	Furniture and constructions made of recovered wooden mussle farm rafts
18	Raimund Beck AG, DE	LignoLoc wooden nails for timber constructions
19	Accsys Technologies, NL	Accoya ultra durable modified wood
20	Donar d.o.o., SI	Modular furniture made of recycled materials
21	Orineo BV, BE	OriBond, plant-based plastic alternatives
22	Lignotrend, DE	LIGNO Cross Laminated Timber construction elements
23	MDF Recovery Ltd, UK	Fibre recovery process for wood fibre board recycling
24	Egger, RO	Wood collection and recycling network for particle boards
25	Fagus Suisse SA, CH	High strength timber for constructions
26	HERSO, NL	Furniture made of recovered wood
27	Termowood, NO	TEWO fast assembly wood construction system
28	Zunami LLC, UKR	Oak lamellas for flooring and pellets from sawdust
29	Holzmühle Westerkamp, DE	Wood flour and fibres for various purposes

Notes: On request of three companies, their applications mentioned in D3.1 Progress Report were finally excluded. * In addition, detailed LCA reports for M-Sora, Aalto Haitek, Unilin and Rilegno are available (cf. D5.2 for detailed results).

5.1.2 Assessment of innovative practices

Table 9 Assessment of identified innovative practices per the 9Rs of the CSCE

Main production sectors of the companies	Good Practice Example	R1-Refuse	R2-Rethink	R3-Reduce	R4-Reuse	R5-Repair	R6-Refurbish	R7-Remanufacture	R8-Repurpose	R9-Recycle
		Make product redundant by abandoning its function or by offering the same function by a radically different (e.g. digital) product or service.	Make product use more intensive (e.g. through product-as-a-service, reuse and sharing models or by putting multi-functional products on the market).	Increase efficiency in product manufacture or use by consuming fewer natural resources and materials.	Reuse of a product which is still in good condition and fulfils its original function (and is not waste) for the same purpose for which it was conceived.	Repair and maintenance of defective product so it can be used with its original function.	Restore an old product and bring it up to date (to specified quality level).	Use parts of a discarded product in a new product with the same function (and as-new-condition).	Use a redundant product or its parts in a new product with different function.	Recover materials from waste to be reprocessed into new products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes.
Wood-based panels	Consorzio Rilegno, IT: national wood collection and recycling network			Optimisation of waste streams and production processes/logistics					Reusing used wood for packaging	Recycling of production rejects and waste wood in particle boards
	Unilin Panels, BE: particleboards made of recycled post-consumer wood			Optimisation of waste streams and production processes/logistics						Recycling of waste wood in particle boards
	MDF Recovery Ltd, UK: Fibre recovery process for wood fibre board recycling			Resource savings through processing of used MDF						Recycling of waste MDF in new MDF boards
	Egger, RO: wood collection and recycling network for particle boards			Optimisation of waste streams and production processes/logistics						Recycling of waste wood in particle boards
	GUTEX, DE: wood fibre insulation panel assembly systems			Optimisation of production processes, use of sawmill and production rejects			Enabling refurbishment of buildings through improved wall insulation			Recycling of sawmill residues
	Fagus GreCon, DE: Formator precision measurement system to reduce material and energy use in wood panel production			Optimisation of production processes and large scale application						
Furniture, interiors, solid wood products	Green Furniture Concept, SE: furniture for large public spaces using natural and upcycled materials		Closing the loop by leasing, maintenance, buy back businesses	Optimisation of production/logistics	Closing the loop through recovery of products after use	Modular eco-design allowing for easy replacement of parts	Restoration of furniture in workshops	Remanufacture of furniture in workshops	Reusing used wood for new furniture	Recycling of wood and other materials
	Valdelia, FR: national professional furniture reuse and recycling network recycling network		Closing the loop by connecting producers, consumers, redistributors	Optimisation of production/logistics	Closing the loop through recovery of products after use	Waste stream management towards repair workshops	Waste stream management towards restoration workshops	Waste stream management towards remanufacturing workshops	Reusing used wood for new furniture	Waste stream management of wood and other materials
	Holy wood, BE: furniture made of recovered wood			Optimisation of production/logistics			Restoration of furniture in workshops	Remanufacture of furniture in workshops	Reusing used wood for new furniture	Recycling of wood and other materials
	HERSO, NL: Furniture made of recovered wood			Optimisation of production/logistics				Remanufacture of furniture in workshops	Reusing used wood for new furniture and interiors	Recycling of wood and other materials
	Melu, SI: doors made of recovered wood			Optimisation of production/logistics					Reusing used wood for new doors	Recycling of wood and other materials
	M SORA, SI: TREESU windows made of recovered wood from old buildings			Optimisation of production/logistics					Reusing wood from old buildings for new windows	Recycling of wood and other materials
	WEBO, NL: circular wooden windows			Optimisation of production/logistics		Modular eco-design allowing for easy replacement of parts			Reusing used wood for new windows	Recycling of wood and other materials
	Donar, SI: modular furniture made of recycled materials			Optimisation of production/logistics		Modular eco-design allowing for easy replacement of parts				Recycling of wood and other materials
Zunami LLC, UKR: oak lamellas for flooring and pellets from sawdust			Optimisation of production/logistics							
Wood construction	Sofrinnov, FR: SYLCAT building system for houses made from wooden pallets	Substitution of fossil-based adhesives, steel and concrete	Closing the loop through direct material redistribution after use	Optimisation of production/logistics	Closing the loop through reuse of materials for initial purpose (pallets)			Reuse of connectors of building parts in new buildings	Reusing used wooden pallets for new buildings	Recycling of wood and other materials
	Tschopp Holzbau, CH: BRESTA glue free, load-bearing ceilings for high acoustic demand	Substitution of fossil-based adhesives, steel and concrete		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics				Reuse of building parts in new buildings	Repurpose of wooden boards is possible	
	Aalto Haitek Oy, FI: wave layered timber building system	Substitution of fossil-based adhesives, steel and concrete		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics				Reuse of building parts in new buildings	Repurpose of wooden parts is possible	
	CREE GmbH, AT: timber-hybrid building design system	Substitution of steel and concrete		Optimisation of production/logistics through digitalisation					Repurpose of modular parts is possible	
	Lignotrend, DE: LIGNO Cross Laminated Timber construction elements	Substitution of fossil-based adhesives, steel and concrete		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics					Repurpose of modular parts is possible	
	Fagus Suisse SA, CH: High strength timber for constructions	Substitution of steel and concrete		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics					Repurpose of wooden parts is possible	
	Termowood, NO: TEWO, fast assembly wood construction system	Substitution of steel and concrete		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics					Repurpose of wooden parts is possible	
Special products, sidestream uses	Raimund Beck AG, DE: wooden nails for timber constructions	Substitution of steel		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics					Wooden nails facilitate repurposing of wooden products	Wooden nails facilitate recycling of wooden products
	Holzmühle Westerkamp, DE: wood flour and fibres for various purposes	Substitution of fossil-based resources		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics						Recycling of sawmill residues
	Orineo BV, BE: OriBond, plant-based plastic alternatives	Substitution of fossil-based binders/adhesives		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics						Recycling of organic residues to natural binders
	Accsys Technologies, NL: Accoya, ultra durable modified wood	Substitution of wood with shorter service life and steel and concrete		Technological innovation and optimisation of production/logistics			Enabling refurbishment of buildings (e.g., durable facades)			
	Fearnmaga, SP: furniture and constructions made of recovered wooden mussle farm rafts			Optimisation of production/logistics					Reusing wood from mussle farms for various products	
Smart tools	RFIDirect Ltd, UK: RFID Smart Wood tags for material and product tracking with embedded passive UHF chips			Optimisation of production processes and large scale application						Digitalized product/material tracking enables decision making on best reuse/recycling options
	Galician Forest Administration, SP: FORTRA tool for wood products value chain tracing			Optimisation of production processes and large scale application						Digitalized product/material tracking enables decision making on best reuse/recycling options

Note: The innovative practices were categorized based on the available information in the application forms and additional materials provided by the companies. It represents an interpretation by the authors to their best understanding of each business case, yet certain features may have been omitted in the material.

5.1.3 Announcement and open call text

wood
CIRCUS Underpinning the vital role of the forest-based sector in the Circular Bio-Economy

Have you got the 3W Factor? WoodCircus invites well performing SMEs in the wood construction value chains to show your talent, share your success story, innovations and ideas for the future. You can win an award for your implemented efficiency solutions or current innovations in **W**ood processing, **W**ood recycling and **W**ood reuse. Your innovative solutions will be assessed by our International Expert Committee. Benefit from the European-wide publicity and communication to **showcase your singularity in the circularity!**

Launched on September 3rd 2019, the 3W Factor is a call for Europe's well performing SMEs in wood construction value chains to step forward with their outstanding best practices. It is launched by the WoodCircus project, a European initiative under the Horizon2020 programme. The project's main goal is to promote wood-based value chains as a key part of a circular bioeconomy in Europe.

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HAVE YOU GOT WHAT IT TAKES?

WoodCircus is all about forest-based products and wood construction but the 3W Factor is not limited to any specific type of production chain or technology! We are glad to welcome all kinds of innovative technological solutions from typical process improvements to more advanced solutions for resource efficiency, recycling and reuse. We are seeking through Europe and beyond to find the best implemented efficiency solutions or current innovations to be approved as best practice for the industry. Take part in shaping tomorrow's European forest-based sector!

- Is your company involved in wood processing and/or manufacturing?
- Have you come up with *the* best solution or innovation in processing and energy efficiency, or recycling and reuse of raw materials, residues, side streams or wood waste?
- Is your solution either a well performing state of the art technology or a progressive innovation with an unconventional, novel approach?

SHOW US YOUR TALENT!

The 3W Factor Proposal Form will appear on the official WoodCircus website (woodcircus.eu) on September 3rd, 2019. We'll be asking some basic information on your company (name, address, website, contact person details, short company profile) and of course a non-confidential description of your outstanding efficiency solution with some evidence provided (savings potential, efficiency gains, sustainability impacts). Should you have any questions concerning the application procedure, you can contact your Regional 3W Contact at any time.

All received proposals will be grouped by region, industry and technology and studied by our International 3W Evaluation Committee*. The Committee reserves the right to give priority to proposals that represent a group of special interest. All proposals are evaluated by the criteria of **INNOVATION** and **COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE** and you may be contacted during the evaluation process to provide additional information.

- **'Innovation'** – Level of technology according to the state of the art, and innovativeness as a progressive approach.
- **'Competitive Advantage'** – Economic feasibility and market relevance, considering also the level of delivered results for efficiency and sustainability (social, economic, environmental), as evidenced through the provided key figures.

Three most innovative solutions will be awarded a gold label and, in addition, the most unique solution will be awarded a special **WoodCircus label**. All winners will profit from Europe-wide communications and will be invited to showcase their efficiency solution at the WoodCircus Conference.

*Names of our International Experts will be published on the project website.

Have you got the 3W Factor?

WoodCircus invites well performing SMEs in the wood construction value chains to participate to the **3W Factor competition for innovative solutions!** Share your outstanding innovations and ideas for the future and win an award for your **implemented efficiency solution or current innovation in wood processing, recycling or reuse.** 3W Factor applications are open, submit your proposal via the application form!

HOW TO APPLY

3W FACTOR APPLICATION FORM

You can submit your 3W Factor application using this form. Please make sure to fill in **all the fields below (1-11).**

We kindly ask you to pay special attention to the questions about Confidential information and Privacy Policy at the end of the form. Should your application contain any confidential information, please contact the Call coordinator Uwe Kies (uwe.kies@innovawood.com) **before any submission.**

10-Confidential information (choose only one)

- No, the submission doesn't include any confidential information and can be distributed among the project consortium and Expert Committee for evaluation purposes.
- Yes, the submission contains confidential information that should remain undisclosed; I have contacted the Call coordinator (uwe.kies@innovawood.com) before submitting the application to agree on how this information shall be treated.

11-Privacy Policy

- Yes, I have read and understood the Privacy Policy and I agree that the data I provide will be collected and stored electronically. My data is used and processed by the WoodCircus consortium and the 3W Factor Expert Committee only for evaluation purposes. By submitting the application form I agree to the processing. [Privacy Policy](#).

2 + 11 =

Submit

CONTACT US

Interested in joining the WoodCircus network? Please use the contact form to get in touch with us or contact directly the WoodCircus Ringmaster :

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